

Boron Carbide and Titanium Diboride Composites

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Modern high performance ceramics as polycrystalline diamond and cubic boron nitride (CBN) compacts as well as aluminum oxide-titanium carbide composites rapidly increase their importance for cutting tools. Nevertheless the significantly high performance of these materials, the high cost prevents their wider applications. The use of an ultra-high pressure processing or a hot-pressing required for the fabrication of those materials result a very high cost.

Boron carbide and titanium diboride composites (BTC), on the other hand, are inexpensive materials and have a possibility of fabrication by pressure-less sintering. Unlike diamond and CBN, in which the intrinsic hardness or strength of the constituents is utilized, while the BTC is hardened and strengthened by a solution hardening or a dispersion strengthening mechanism. The obtained hardness derived from those mechanisms in many ceramics is usually much lower than that of diamond and CBN compacts. In the case of BTC, however, the hardness by those mechanisms is exceptionally high and possibly comparable to that of diamond and CBN compacts (Fig.1).

In this paper, an experimental and analytical studies for obtaining a high performance and low cost ceramics were described. The BTC of boron carbide with a content of 3 to 90 percent of titanium diboride were examined. The BTC with density of 99% and above of the theoretical value were obtained by the sintering under a pressure-less conditions with constituent powders of submicron size (Fig.2). The BTC thus obtained consists of two phases, the pure titanium diboride and the solid solution of boron carbide at ambient temperature. The hardness of the composites caused by the precipitation of titanium diboride phase, is comparable to that of diamond and CBN compacts. Those results were confirmed by metallography, X-ray diffraction, electron microprobe analysis and mechanical tests. Other properties of BTC, oxidation resistance and thermal shock, for example, were also examined.

